

Measuring service quality dimensions affecting customer satisfaction in the airline sector: A case study for improving airline service in a post-pandemic world.

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Acknowledgments

I declare that I have personally prepared this report and that it has not in whole or in part been submitted for any other degree or qualification. Nor has it appeared in whole or in part in any textbook, journal or any other document previously published or produced for any purpose. The work described here is my/our own, carried out personally unless otherwise stated. All sources of information, including quotations, are acknowledged by means of reference, both in the final reference section and at the point where they occur in the text.

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Abstract

Covid-19 paralyzed global aviation as nations shutdown their borders and imposed lock-downs and other restrictions with each country taking a very cautious view on border re-openings. Since early 2020, when the pandemic crushed global air travel, a multitude of airlines have either entered bankruptcy or were liquidated (Kotoky, 2022). The pandemic and its effects wiped out 15 years of worldwide passenger growth in a matter of months, reducing 2020 flight capacity to levels not seen since 2005 (Cirium Analytics and Bowen, 2021).

The primary goal of this study is to examine the effects of service quality and customer value in the airline sector to improve business efficiency and effectiveness in a post-pandemic setting. A literature review was conducted looking into the different research methods of customer service dimensions (SERVQUAL). It was found that an analysis of inflight services and airport logistics using novel classification models had not yet been applied. Three major US airlines, United Airlines, American Airlines and Delta Airlines, are the context for the study. The research design focuses on customer satisfaction drivers through grab-sample surveys using the 5-point Likert “psychometric response scale” (Preedy and Watson, 2010) for the Social Sciences. Regression analysis was applied for hypothesis testing and this study uses 10 classification models including LightGBM, AdaBoost and Keras NN which is a first in the analysis of airline customer service. Findings show correlations between satisfaction and the type of travel to be the most important feature followed by online/mobile check-in and inflight WiFi.

This study adds to the body of knowledge regarding customer satisfaction and the selected service quality drivers and dimensions of airlines. In order to increase airline passengers' satisfaction, recommendations were made for the creation of marketing strategies as well as for enhancing service quality and product quality (customer value). These suggestions will ultimately improve the airline industry's growth and profitability in a sector that is restructuring and recovering from the effects of Covid-19.

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1.0 Introduction

Using the Z-score method to measure of the financial stability of companies (CFI, 2022), six airlines in Asia were found to be at risk for bankruptcy where domestic air traffic is still 61% below pre-pandemic levels, versus about 25% for Europe and only 0.5% in the U.S. Major airlines such as Thai Airways and Virgin Airways have filed for bankruptcy and most airlines worldwide have had to restructure. Since the majority of Japanese and Chinese airlines are either funded by government or have strong ties to regulators, their majors will continue to be financially stable. Likewise, major US airlines backed by unions will have the ability to advocate for access to government subsidies. Markets are now heading in a positive direction, with domestic short-haul markets recovering first. China and other local markets are currently seeing expansion, while the US and Brazil are not far behind. It will take longer for long-haul markets to recover. In 2022 traffic is expected to grow by 47% back to 2015 levels (Cirium Analytics and Bowen, 2021).

Customer service is the most important variable that a company has to manage (Baggs and Kleiner, 1996). The airline industry is restructuring and in need of a major boost to traffic capacity growth, therefore customer service will become more important than ever.

The service sector accounts for roughly 60% of annual GDP and nearly 70% of new job creation in the United States, making it the world leader in service sector growth (Behn and Riley, 1999). Several studies have been conducted to improve service efficiency and to identify the factors that influence customer satisfaction and loyalty in various industries (Behn and Riley, 1999). The factors that best distinguish between passengers who are loyal to an airline and those who are not include frequent flyer status, pricing, the airline's status as a national carrier, and airline brand image among friends. For instance, loyalty programs are important for business passengers, yet it is challenging to pinpoint a single element for leisure travelers' airline loyalty (Dolnicar et al., 2011). No computed model identified customer satisfaction as a major factor influencing airline loyalty.

For in-flight satisfaction services provided by cabin attendants, aircraft facilities, airport services and inflight products are the most tangible and direct to consumers and thus passengers choose to evaluate airlines' value based on their level of satisfaction with these tangibles (Park et al., 2004). Consequently, one of the key ingredients for an airline's success is enhancing the quality of its in-flight services. In particular, the quality of in-flight WiFi and online/mobile check-

in systems are key components of in-flight services. Numerous studies done on the airline industry have tried to categorize service quality impacts, however there isn't much observational study on the importance of efficient in-flight service. Knowing that long-haul markets will take longer to recover than domestic short-haul markets, the impact of short-haul flights and long-haul flights on the value of inflight services is also examined in this study by creating new modeling features from the short-haul and long-haul data. The influence of business and leisure travel on the value of inflight services is also compared as it is historically challenging to pinpoint a single element for leisure travelers' airline loyalty.

A review of the literature on airline service quality, both in flight and airport level, is presented in this study. A procedure for a research methodology using 10 classification models and comparing the precision of the models as well as analyzing the important features of the dataset is introduced. A novel neural network API for analytics practitioners to adopt in their research of customer satisfaction research is also presented. The motivation behind the study was to examine how impactful airline services are to customer value and how they could be used, designed and adapted to make significant business decisions.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Service Quality

Service quality (SERVQUAL) is a comparison of customer expectation and the actual delivery of service (Sugiarto Sigit and Octaviana Vivi, 2021). Service quality is key to customer value in that the customer will continue to buy from a business and stay loyal if the service quality meets or exceeds the customer's expectations. In general, when a consumer compares service expectations to a company's performance, they are referring to service quality. The facilities, services, and personnel appearance are defined as tangibles. The ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately is defined as reliability. The service will be considered excellent, if perceptions exceed expectations; it will be regarded as good or adequate, if it only equals the expectations; the service will be classed as bad, poor or deficient, if it does not meet them. Parasuraman et al. developed a scale for measuring service quality, which is known as SERVQUAL. This scale expresses service quality by calculating the difference between expectations and perceptions, evaluating both in relation to the five service quality dimensions known as 'tangibles', 'reliability', 'responsiveness', 'assurance' and 'empathy' (Parasuraman et al., 1988).

Figure 1. GAP Model

Source: (Parasuraman et al., 1988)

Dimension	Definition
Tangibles	Appearance of physical facilities, equipment, personnel and written materials
Reliability	Ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately
Responsiveness	Willingness to help customers and provide prompt service
Assurance	Employees' knowledge and courtesy and their ability to inspire trust and confidence
Empathy	Caring, easy access, good /communication, customer understanding and individualized attention given to cutomers

Figure 2. Five Dimensions of Service Quality (Parasuraman et al., 1988)

The SERVQUAL scale has been tested and adapted in many studies conducted in diverse service settings, cultural contexts and geographic locations and industries such as healthcare, fast-food, education, retail and hospitality (Parasuraman et al., 1988).

Improving service quality is dependent on the airline's ability to meet up to customers' expectations. Loyalty is a repeated choice (Dolnicar et al., 2011) therefore by delivering continued quality service, airlines can strengthen the relationship with the customer, stay competitive, improve brand image and by extension turn higher profits. Loyalty reward programs such as Frequent Flyer Programs are a representation of repeated choices that customers make when airlines meet customer expectations. Airlines must therefore appreciate the competitive significance of efficiency: Long-term quality improvement is an expense that yields higher profits (Kandampully and Suhartanto, 2000).

"Fear of illness, economic damage, and stigma have had a devastating impact on the travel industry and have caused a significant reduction in both business and leisure travel." (Lamb et al., 2021). During the pandemic masks and disinfectants were not only the norm, they were mandated by government. In a post-pandemic world, social and emotional perspectives of airline passengers such as trust, fear, and proximity to passengers will have to be taken into consideration. Cleanliness and etiquette will be high on the list of customer expectations. This will be a new focus for airlines as cleanliness has traditionally taken a back-seat to other necessities such as WiFi and inflight entertainment. The need for a clean environment has become important in a post-Covid-19 environment. Implementing cleanliness as part of a a re-design in tourists' experiences has become a part of recovery in hotel & tourism (Awan et al., 2020). There is a distinction between actual cleanliness and the perception of cleanliness. Actual cleanliness refers to observed cleanliness, what can actually be seen. Objective

measures, such as actual cleanliness, are considered a less biased view of the environment than the perception of cleanliness is (Vos et al., 2018). There are three cleanliness dimensions. The most important cleanliness dimensions are food, flight attendants' presentation and lavatory hygiene (Park and Almanza, 2020). An essential element of service quality, there is no compromising with cleanliness. In fact, customers have made decisions to choose, stay or come back to a business based upon cleanliness (Barber and Scarcelli, 2010). In a new travel environment, cleanliness will likely make or break a business's opportunity to keep customers. Cleanliness can literally increase customer service satisfaction while uncleanliness can decrease satisfaction (Vos et al., 2018).

2.2 Airline Business Model

Understanding the components and factors of an airline's ability to deliver quality service necessitates understanding its business model. The forms of business models in the airline industry are presented in terms of how the carrier generates revenue, its product offering, value-added services, revenue sources, and target customers.

There are three main airline business models: Full-service carrier (FSC), Low-cost carrier (LCC) and Charter carrier or (CC) (Rozenberg et al., 2014). The FSC and LCC models are explained below as they pertain to customer satisfaction in the public scope.

Full-service carrier (FSC)

A full-service carrier (FSC) is generally an airline company created from a former government-owned airline and via deregulation, into an airline company with the following attributes describing its business model (Lange and Bier, 2019). These are regarded as the major carriers.

Product differentiation: This is affected by in-flight and ground service, online and mobile check-in) and travel rules.

Customer relationship management: For example, the frequent flyers programs are an aspect part customer relationship management (CRM). The goal of CRM is to improve passengers' travelling experience to customize the airline's services and products. CRM allows an airline to differentiate their product.

Sales channels: Sales channels include external travel agencies or external online travel agents.

Distribution system: The complexity of an airline's distribution system is supported by external technology companies called Global Distribution Systems (GDSs). Among the most used GDSs are Galileo, Amadeus, Worldspan, Sabre (Magdalina and Bouzaima, 2021).

Low-Cost Carriers (LCC)

An LCC is as an airline designed to have a competitive advantage in terms of costs (Lange and Bier, 2019). In order to maintain this advantage, an LCC relies on a comparably simplified business model encompassing:

Aircraft usage: The aircraft is in the air more hours a day compared with full-service carries that are required to adhere to the connectivity schedule (Magdalina and Bouzaima, 2021).

Service with no extras: The low-cost carrier is not compared with the full service carrier as they do not offer lounge services at airports, seat selection, in-flight service, and a frequent flyer program. The tickets are non-refundable and there is no option to rebook with other carriers.

Minimized sales/reservation costs: All tickets are e-tickets and the distribution system is online or the direct sales centers and passengers themselves receive flight details via e-mail. The low-cost carrier does not communicate with travel agents and Global Distribution Systems (GDS) companies.

Additional services: Low-cost carriers have additional revenue sources besides ticket sales. Some include commissions from hotels and car rental companies, credit card fees, (excess) luggage fees, in-flight food and beverages, and advertising space.

Figure 3: FSC/LCC Business Model

Source: (Sabre Airline Solutions, 2010)

Examining the business model gives a clearer understanding that the ability to deliver quality customer service is influenced and dependent on relationships airlines have with other businesses. Aside from service expectations, transaction and switching costs for customers have a huge impact on customer loyalty (NGUYEN et al., 2020). It is much more difficult to consider the efficiency of airline services than it is for other service providers such as banking institutions whose work processes consist of different but internal affairs. Airline services on the other hand, are supported simultaneously by a multitude of agencies, divisions and partners with their own operations and logistics such as the TSA, airport authority, catering firms, hotels aka “coopetition” (Bahar, 2022) and other partners (Soliman and Fouad, 2019). Consequently, it is much more difficult to main a high level of service when service is affected by many variables. Improving the efficiency of airline services necessitates the coordination of different operations by several organizations.

To summarize, there have been ample studies in customer service mostly related to retail or hotel & tourism, however empirical evidence is lacking on air travel quality (AIRQUAL), within the airline sector (Jiang and Zhang, 2016). Notably, there is little to no research on examining what the expectations of customers will be in the airline sector post Covid-19.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Data Collection

The research design focuses on several customer satisfaction drivers collected through grab-sampling surveys. The scale that the survey uses is undisclosed, but considering it is a customer satisfaction survey with responses from zero to five, it is likely that it is using the 5-point Likert “psychometric response scale” (Preedy and Watson, 2010) for the Social Sciences.

The Likert Scale is defined as follows:

0 = Does not apply

1 = Very dissatisfied

2 = Moderately dissatisfied

3 = Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied

4 = Moderately satisfied

5 = Very satisfied

It's important to understand that a zero rating does not equate to dissatisfied. A particular service may not exist on certain flights, or a passenger may have not requested or expected the service. For the sake of this study, rating number three “Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied” is renamed to “Not Satisfied” for clarity as it has been shown that using the two highest values on feedback surveys is the most accurate predictor of customer retention (Qualtrics, 2022).

The first step of the process was to gather the data required as input variables and target class variables within the simple logit model. The target class for the model was Satisfaction and the remaining columns were used as inputs. Three major US airlines, United Airlines, American Airlines and Delta Airlines, are the context for the dataset. The dataset includes approximately 130,000 survey responses as well as passenger information, flight information and airline service data. There are 21 columns with a single binary target class satisfaction column. 14 of the columns are service/product ratings from zero to five for example, Wi-Fi Service, Legroom,

Onboard Service, Seat Comfort. Passenger information was also included such as the purpose of travel and age as well as flight distance.

Dataset Columns:

Gender: (Female, Male)

Customer Type: (Loyal customer, Disloyal customer)
Renamed to Repeat and New Customer in this study.

Age: Passenger age.

Type of Travel: Purpose of travel. (Personal Travel, Business Travel)

Class: Cabin class. (Business, Eco, Eco Plus)
Renamed to Business, Economy Plus and Economy in this study.

Flight Distance: The flight distance of the trip.

Inflight Wi-Fi Service: Satisfaction level of the inflight Wi-Fi service.

Departure/Arrival Time Convenience: Satisfaction level of the departure/arrival times.

Ease of Online booking: Satisfaction level of online booking. Web/mobile reservations.
Renamed to Online Booking in this study.

Gate Location: Satisfaction level of gate location.

Food and Drink: Satisfaction level of food and drinks.

Online Boarding: Satisfaction level of online boarding. Web/mobile check-in.
Renamed to Online Checkin.

Seat Comfort: Satisfaction level of seat comfort.

Inflight Entertainment: Satisfaction level of inflight entertainment.

On-board Service: Satisfaction level of on-board service. Amenities.

Legroom service: Satisfaction level of legroom.

Baggage Handling: Satisfaction level of baggage handling.

Check-in Service: Satisfaction level of check-in service.
Renamed to Airport Checkin.

Inflight Service: Satisfaction level of inflight service. Cabin crew service, attention.

Cleanliness: Satisfaction level of cleanliness.

Departure Delay in Minutes: Minutes delayed at departure.

Arrival Delay in Minutes: Minutes delayed at arrival.

Satisfaction: Airline satisfaction level (Satisfaction, neutral or dissatisfaction).
Renamed to Satisfaction and Not Satisfied.

3.2 Data Processing

After the data had been extracted and the required data was verified, it was important to process the data to find any missing data or anomalies. The first step was to clean the data using Python. Python is a general-purpose, high-level, interpreted programming language. It is created under an OSI-approved open-source license, making it freely usable and distributable, even for commercial use, and its design philosophy places an emphasis on code readability (Srinath, 2017). There are more than 200,000 Python packages in the world (and that's just counting those hosted on PyPI, the official Python Package Index). Python is used more for development and machine learning deployment as well as data analysis and statistics. As of this writing Python is currently number one on the TIOBE Index. This is mainly due to the popularity of data science, machine learning and deep learning as it is a highly readable language that non-programmers can pick up relatively quickly compared with lower-level languages like C or C++.

395 rows (0.3%) of the Arrival Delay column had missing data. Even though it's an insignificant number of samples with missing data, imputation was done by replacing the missing values with the delay times from the Departure Delay column as that is much more accurate than imputation by the mean value in a dataset where the distribution range is wide. Missing data or the improper handling of missing data can affect bias and have significant effects on research (NGUYEN et al., 2020).

Gender	Customer Type	Age	Type of Travel	Class	Flight Distance	Inflight Wifi	Dep/Arr Times	Online Booking	Gate Location	Food and Drinks	Online Checkin	Seat Comfort	Inflight Entertainment	Onboard Service	Legroom	Baggage Handling	Airport Checkin	Inflight Service	Cleanliness	Departure Delay	Arrival Delay	Satisfaction
Male	Repeat Customer	13	Personal Travel	Economy	460	3	4	3	1	5	3	5	5	4	3	4	4	5	5	25	18	Not Satisfied
Male	New Customer	25	Business Travel	Business	235	3	2	3	3	1	3	1	1	1	5	3	1	4	1	1	6	Not Satisfied
Female	Repeat Customer	26	Business Travel	Business	1142	2	2	2	2	5	5	5	5	4	3	4	4	4	5	0	0	Satisfied
Female	Repeat Customer	25	Business Travel	Business	562	2	5	5	5	2	2	2	2	2	5	3	1	4	2	11	9	Not Satisfied
Male	Repeat Customer	61	Business Travel	Business	214	3	3	3	3	4	5	5	3	3	4	4	3	3	3	0	0	Satisfied
Female	Repeat Customer	26	Personal Travel	Economy	1180	3	4	2	1	1	2	1	1	3	4	4	4	4	1	0	0	Not Satisfied
Male	Repeat Customer	47	Personal Travel	Economy	1276	2	4	2	3	2	2	2	2	3	3	4	3	5	2	9	23	Not Satisfied
Female	Repeat Customer	52	Business Travel	Business	2035	4	3	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	4	4	0	Satisfied
Female	Repeat Customer	41	Business Travel	Business	853	1	2	2	2	4	3	3	1	1	2	1	4	1	2	0	0	Not Satisfied
Male	New Customer	20	Business Travel	Economy	1061	3	3	3	4	2	3	3	2	2	3	4	4	3	2	0	0	Not Satisfied
Female	New Customer	24	Business Travel	Economy	1182	4	5	5	4	2	5	2	2	3	3	5	3	5	2	0	0	Not Satisfied
Female	Repeat Customer	12	Personal Travel	Economy	308	2	4	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	5	5	5	1	0	0	Not Satisfied
Male	Repeat Customer	53	Business Travel	Economy	834	1	4	4	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	4	4	1	28	8	Not Satisfied
Male	Repeat Customer	33	Personal Travel	Economy	946	4	2	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	5	2	2	2	4	0	0	Satisfied
Female	Repeat Customer	26	Personal Travel	Economy	453	3	2	3	2	2	3	2	2	4	3	2	2	1	2	43	35	Not Satisfied
Male	New Customer	13	Business Travel	Economy	486	2	1	2	3	4	2	1	4	2	1	4	1	3	4	1	0	Not Satisfied
Female	Repeat Customer	26	Business Travel	Business	2123	3	3	3	3	4	4	4	4	5	3	4	5	4	4	49	51	Satisfied
Male	Repeat Customer	41	Business Travel	Business	2075	4	4	2	4	4	4	4	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	0	10	Satisfied
Female	Repeat Customer	45	Business Travel	Business	2486	4	4	4	4	3	4	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	4	7	5	Satisfied
Male	Repeat Customer	38	Personal Travel	Economy	460	2	3	3	2	5	3	5	5	1	2	4	3	2	5	17	18	Not Satisfied
Male	Repeat Customer	9	Business Travel	Economy	1174	2	4	2	4	2	2	1	2	1	5	3	4	3	2	0	4	Not Satisfied

Figure 4. Cleaned dataset

The data is more understandable from a statistical point of view and more readable and suitable for model building.

- Columns renamed to more conventional naming conventions for readability
- Columns reordered
- Data types were made congruous
- Imputation of Arrival Delay NaNs using the replace method
- Columns reindexed
- Id column dropped after copying the dataframe
- Transformation of target label into binary integers

3.3 Exploratory Data Analysis

Before a simple logit model can be implemented, it is important to examine the data for any trends or outliers that may affect the results of the logit model or provide initial insights and direction. Often EDA can spark ideas and statistical analysis that wasn't imagined before. EDA has the potential to yield both theoretical and practical benefits (Braun and Oswald, 2011).

For preliminary EDA the statistics of the data are examined to better understand the data such as count, mean, standard deviation, min/max, and quartiles. This data might not be used directly in the research, but it's better to start out with a clear understanding of the data. The statistics for the data are illustrated below in Figure 4.

	Age	Flight Distance	Inflight Wifi	Dep/Arr Times	Online Booking	Gate Location	Food and Drinks	Online Checkin	Seat Comfort	Inflight Entertainment
count	129880	129880	129880	129880	129880	129880	129880	129880	129880	129880
mean	39.4279566	1190.31639	2.72869572	3.05759932	2.75687558	2.97692485	3.20477364	3.2526332	3.44136126	3.358076686
std	15.11936	997.452477	1.32934014	1.52674149	1.40173961	1.27851967	1.32993307	1.35071877	1.31928888	1.334048983
min	7	31	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25%	27	414	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
50%	40	844	3	3	3	3	3	3	4	4
75%	51	1744	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	4
max	85	4983	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

	Onboard Service	Legroom	Baggage Handling	Airport Checkin	Inflight Service	Cleanliness	Departure Delay	Arrival Delay
count	129880	129880	129880	129880	129880	129880	129880	129880
mean	3.38302279	3.35087773	3.63211426	3.30626732	3.64219279	3.28632584	14.7137127	15.1601016
std	1.28709935	1.31625177	1.18002457	1.26618533	1.17666907	1.31368223	38.0711262	38.5996009
min	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
25%	2	2	3	3	3	2	0	0
50%	4	4	4	3	4	3	0	0
75%	4	4	5	4	5	4	12	13
max	5	5	5	5	5	5	1592	1584

Figure 5. Summary Statistics

Looking at Figure 4, The mean age is almost 40 years old with a deviation of 15 years. The bottom quarter are 27 years old or younger and the top quarter are 51 years old or older. The youngest passenger is 7 years old and the oldest passenger is 81 years old. The average flight distance is 1,200 miles with a standard deviation of 1000 which is quite large. The minimum distance flown is 31 miles (50km) which could either be an outlier or a short charter. The max distance is almost 5,000 miles (8,000km) which is clearly a long-haul international flight. The top quarter of flights are 1,744 miles (2806km), and the bottom quarter are 414 miles (666km) or less. The majority of flights are between 415 miles (667km) and 1743 miles (2807km).

Figure 6. Flight Distance and Satisfaction

The longer the flight, the more passengers are satisfied. A possible explanation is that there are more passengers in business class on longer flights and therefore are more satisfied due to better services and comfort. Another possibility is that passengers on longer flights are likely repeat customers and therefore no what to expect and are thus satisfied. It could also be psychological. Passengers on long flights could be vacationing or visiting relatives and are more inclined to be satisfied overall. It could also be lower perceptions of service quality, resulting in more satisfied passengers traveling on long-haul (Ismail and Jiang, 2019).

The average departure delay is 14 minutes which is pretty respectable. The minimum departure delay was zero and the max was 1592 minutes or 26.5 hours. That seems incredible and likely due to winter storms. The mean arrival delay is 15 minutes, the minimum arrival delay is 0 and the max is also around the same 26 hour mark indicating that was likely the same flight. Which also means that flight was actually on time on its second flight attempt. Many factors, including weather conditions, airport and airspace congestion, and use of smaller aircraft, have been implicated as reasons of flight delays. The hub and spoke network structure and other operational factors have a big impact on the scheduled on-time arrival probability.

Last but not least, full-service airlines place a higher value on the cost of late arrivals than do low-cost carriers, and taking the cheapest flight on a route reduces the likelihood of arriving on time as scheduled (Deshpande and Arikan, 2012).

Figure 7. Linear relationship between Departure and Arrival Delays

There is a linear relationship between departure and arrival delays which makes sense. Surprisingly, a customer is satisfied even after an average total delay of 1300 minutes or 21 hours. With this linear relationship, it could be beneficial to create a Total Delay variable and examine that new feature later in the research.

3.3.1 Output & Input Variables

Graphs arouse human’s perceptual system to make perceptual inference. Graphs in data analysis group together all relevant information and avoid a large number of non-relevant information (Larkin and Simon, 1987). This study uses the Python Seaborn Library for graphs. The Viridis color palette was chosen for its colorblind friendliness.

Figure 8. Ratio of Satisfied to Not Satisfied

The target class is fairly balanced with 57% of passengers dissatisfied and 43% of passengers satisfied. Using a Python function to look further at satisfaction, 52% of females are neutral or dissatisfied, 56% of males are also neutral or dissatisfied. The almost even split between male and female indicates that this independent variable is likely not very useful. 52% of loyal customers or repeat customers are neutral or dissatisfied and 76% of disloyal or new customers are neutral or dissatisfied. 58% of customers traveling on business are satisfied and almost 90% of customers traveling on leisure are neutral or dissatisfied. 69% of passengers in Business class are satisfied, 81% of passengers from Economy are neutral or dissatisfied and 75% of passengers in Economy Plus passengers are neutral or dissatisfied. With basic EDA it is evident that most of the loyal repeat customers are likely the same passengers traveling on business and flying in business class.

Figure 9. Relationship between Age and Customer Type

From the box diagram in Figure 9, it's evident that most of the airline's loyal repeat customers are between the ages of 30 and 54 with the average age being about 42 years of age. The majority of the new customers is between the ages of 25 to 35 with the average being about 29 years of age. Looking at the right graph in Figure 9 above, four age modes are visible between 5-22, 23-38, 39-53, 54-69, and 70-81. Older the customers are more loyal repeat customers and likely frequent flyer clubbers. There is a huge mode of new disloyal customers between the ages of 20-28. They are likely first-time flyers on their chosen airline or found themselves on flights without WiFi. Continuing on, 42% of customers are loyal repeat customers who are neutral or dissatisfied, 14% of passengers are disloyal new customers who are neutral or dissatisfied. A revealing statistic is found in the scatter plot in Figure 10 below. There is a blue horizontal band of new disloyal customers between the ages of 31 and 36 who are not satisfied regardless of flight distance.

Figure 10. Disloyal and Not Satisfied customers 31-36

Additional initial observations discovered from exploratory data analysis:

- 129880 survey respondents and 22 features excluding the “id” and “target” columns.
- Average flight delay is 15 minutes with a deviation of 38 minutes.
- Median flight delay is 0 telling us that 50% of the flights were not delayed.
- Female respondents account for 50.74% of the dataset.
- 393 missing values in the “Arrival Delay in Minutes” column account for 0.3% of the dataset.
- Loyal customers make up 81.69% of the dataset.

- Business travelers account for 69.06% of the population.
- 47.86% of the passengers are traveling on Business Class. The rest are distributed in Economy and Economy Plus classes.
- 56.55% of customers are not satisfied with airline services and product offerings.

Of the two features that were found to be most important in this study, these statistics were discovered.

- 22% rated WiFi 4 or 5 and were satisfied.
- 12% rated WiFi 2 or 3 and were still satisfied.
- 8% rated WiFi 4 or 5 and were still not satisfied.
- 30% rated WiFi 2 or 3 and were not satisfied.
- 36% rated online checkin 4 or 5 and were satisfied
- 3% rated online checkin 1 or 2 and were still satisfied
- 14% rated online checkin 4 or 5 and were still not satisfied
- 24% rated online checkin 1 or 2 and were not satisfied

Looking at the mean of the ratings of the services:

Inflight Service	3.642193
Inflight Wifi	2.728696
Online Checkin	3.252633

Initial exploration also shows that Inflight Wifi, Inflight Service and Online Checkin will (potentially) be important features.

4.0 Feature Engineering & Transformations

"The success of all Machine Learning algorithms depends on how you present the data." (Pezeshki, 2017).

Feature engineering involves taking raw data and turning it into information inputs that the predictive models can use to more accurately predict the outcome of new never-before-seen data. Feature engineering also allows for the discovery of new insights as it gives the practitioner a chance to view the data through a different lens per se. The characteristics of your data will impact the predictive models you run and the outcomes you achieve. Feature engineering allows a practitioner to implement less complex models that are easier to handle,

more performant, and easier to understand as the data becomes easier for the model to understand as well. It's also possible that a practitioner might use less-than-optimal parameters, but if the features are engineered well, they can still obtain fairly good results. Feature engineering allows the best models and most optimized parameters to be chosen with less effort. With good features, you can more accurately identify the underlying problem and get a representation of all the data you have in front of you. However, while creating new features can make your model and predictions better, this is not always the case. Feature engineering is not a one-stop-shop for prediction success.

In this analysis, Flight Distance is also an attribute of the dataset that differentiates other services therefore, new features named "Shorthaul" and Longhaul" were created in this study. There are 10,327 long haul flights. The average distance is 3,514 miles (5655 km). The shortest flight is 3,000 miles (4,828 km) and the longest flight is 4,983 miles (8,019 km). American Airlines categorizes short-haul and long-haul flights as less than 3,000 miles, and more 3,000 miles respectively. Binning short-haul and long-haul features might provide additional insights. Using Python's Boolean methods, flights will be binned into less than 3,000 miles (short-haul) or equal to or greater than 3,000 miles (long-haul).

Satisfaction	Route	Size	Percentage
Not Satisfied	Shorthaul	71114	37.3
Satisfied	Shorthaul	48439	6.15
Not Satisfied	Longhaul	2338	54.75
Satisfied	Longhaul	7989	1.8

Figure 11. Proportion of Satisfied and Not Satisfied against Route

Figure 11 above shows statistics uncovered using the new short-haul and long-haul features. Summing the values, Not satisfied short-haul passengers count for 43.45%, long-haul passengers make up 56.55%.

Figure 12. Proportion of Satisfied to Not Satisfied by Route

Plotting the same percentage ratios is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 13. Age distribution of passengers against Routes

Here the Boxen plot is used to illustrate age distribution of satisfied passengers between short-haul and long-haul flights. The Boxen plot or “letter-value plot” as the authors named it, provides a better representation of the distribution of the data than the boxplot but without the need to choose specific parameters. The Boxen plot is similar to the boxplot but includes more quantiles for better visualization (Moon et al., 2022). Traditional Boxplots may have an excessive number of outliers and display less data about the distribution. In letter-value plots (Boxenplots), the

median (Q2, 50%) serves as the starting point. Half of the remaining data are contained in each level that follows. Half of the data is located in the first two segments from the centerline. The remaining two sections together make up 25% of the data after that. This goes on until the level of any outliers is reached. Every level outward is shaded lighter. The Boxen plot in Figure 12 demonstrates that older passengers on both short-haul and long-haul flights are on the average more satisfied. The majority of satisfied passengers on short-haul flights are between 30-50 and the majority of passengers who are satisfied on long-haul flights are between the ages of 38-50.

Figure 14. Class distribution against Route

Remarkably, only 0.1% (75 passengers) flew in economy. This says that all the passengers in the grab-sample survey who flew long-haul were flying in Business class. More than half of the passengers on short-haul flights were in Economy Class. It has been found that passengers preferred activity on long-haul flights is relaxing, working followed by inflight entertainment (Alamdari, 1999). Given this data, it makes sense that most passengers flying long-haul would want to fly in Business Class.

Figure 15. Linear relationship of flight delays

Previously in the data exploration section 3.3, the scatter plot demonstrated a linear relationship between the departure and arrival delays which makes sense since most of the time departure delays will carry over to arrivals. As can be seen in Figure 15 above, after imputation of the missing values in the arrival delay column by replacing the corresponding rows from the departure delay column, the linear relationship was more pronounced. In this feature engineering step both delays were binned into a single Total Delay input. As shown in the categorical swarm plot in Figure 16 below, there are many more delays with short-haul flights with one flight being delayed 58 hours. This is most definitely due to winter or storm weather conditions. Overall, there are more delays with short-haul flights due to the nature of hub-cities. Flights from numerous “spoke” cities in a hub-and-spoke network transport passengers to a major “hub” city. Flights from various spoke cities arrive at the hub virtually simultaneously in order to provide timely connections to final destinations. Consequently, a delayed flight often causes all subsequent flights to be delayed (Bhat, 1995).

Figure 16. Swarm Plot showing Total Delay against Route

Figure 16 above revealing outliers in the Route feature. A swarmplot “beeswarm” is a plot available from Python’s Seaborn library. It is a kind of scatter plot that resembles a strip layout. It is utilized to represent categorical values more effectively. Additionally, it is used to prevent point overlap.

4.1 Feature Selection

The representation of data in real-world learning issues frequently makes use of several data inputs or features where only a small subset of which may actually connected to the analytics goal or idea. In this case, feature selection is crucial to accelerating learning and enhancing concept quality (Kira and Rendell, 1992). Feature selection is one of the most common and significant methods for pre-processing data. It is an essential step in the machine learning process. In statistics and machine learning, it is sometimes referred to as variable selection, attribute selection, or variable subset selection. It involves finding pertinent features and eliminating unnecessary, redundant, or noisy data. This procedure if used well, can improve predicted accuracy and make data more understandable (Kumar and Minz, 2014). The usual applications of FS are in classification, clustering, and regression tasks. Pre-processing is performed to make the dataset smaller so that analysis can be done more quickly and to make the dataset more suited to the analysis method that has been chosen. With an abundance of developed analysis methods available as a part of a researcher’s toolset and the fact that big data is now common-place, reducing the size of the dataset is the more common usage. Both feature set reduction and sample set reduction can be used to reduce the size of datasets. Reducing the amount of features in a dataset so that it is comparable to the number of samples

prevents model overfitting, which by extension produces better results on validation datasets. Additionally, building models from datasets with a lot of features requires additional computational power (Jović et al., 2015).

4.1.1 Feature Selection Methods

In this study One-hot-encoding, the Kernel Density Estimate plot, the ColumnTransformer method from Python's Scikitlearn library, a Correlation Heatmap from Seaborn's package, and Lasso Regression with the LASSO Path plot is used in feature selection.

4.1.2 One-hot-encoding

One Hot Encoding is a data processing and transformation method that improves a model's comprehension of the data. One-hot Encoding is used when the categorical variables are not ordinal like the Type of Customer and Type of Travel columns in this dataset. It is also used when the number of categorical features is less than the continuous features so that they can be used in machine learning. Sometimes the most useful characteristics are categorical and cannot be modeled by regression. Some of these categorical features can be converted into numerous binary features (0/1) using one-hot encoding. Then the presence or absence of each individual categorical unit (cardinal value) can then be fitted into the linear regression. One of the issues of one-hot-encoding is that practitioners commonly choose to drop all of the cardinal values leaving only one reference value behind. This means that rich associations between labels that can be used during training are ignored by one-hot encoding (Rodríguez et al., 2018). In this study, all the categorical units (cardinal values) have been kept as to use all possible data that might be useful.

4.1.3 Kernel Density Estimation (KDE)

Similar to a histogram, a kernel density estimate (KDE) plot is a technique for displaying the distribution of observations in a dataset. KDE uses a continuous probability density curve in one or more dimensions to represent the data. To show the probability distribution of one variable with relation to the other values, KDE can plot the data against several data variables or bivariate variables. The KDE can be used to identify skewness in data and categorical variables that may not need to be included in model development saving time and computational

resources. In contrast to the histogram, the KDE generates a smooth estimate of the probability density function, employs the locations of all the sample points, and more strongly implies multimodality. It is a must-have enabling the user to better analyze the studied probability distribution (Węglarczyk, 2018).

Figure 17. Flight Distance and Gender KDE plots

Observing the KDE plot, Flight Distance is moderately right-skewed. It will be worth examining its skewness value and make a judgment based on the goal and dimensions of the dataset to determine if the model will benefit from transforming it to a more normal distribution. Gender proportions are almost identical and provide no benefit in including it in the model building stage.

4.1.4 Column Transformer & Log Transformation

There are many instances where researchers may want to normalize a variable. First, there is the (often problematic) assumption of normality of the outcome (conditional on the covariates) in the classical linear regression problem. One technique that is still somewhat popular in this context is to “beat the data” (Peterson, 2021) to look normal via some kind of normalizing transformation. This could be something as simple as a log transformation or something as complex as a Yeo-Johnson transformation (Yeo and Johnson, 2000). While perhaps not the most elegant solution to the problem, often, this technique works well as a quick solution. Another increasingly popular application of normalization occurs in applied regression settings with highly skewed distributions of the covariates (Kuhn et al., 2013). Essentially, data

normalization is used to maintain consistency across all records. It helps create a single base of truth and guarantee data integrity. The goal of data normalization is to eliminate data redundancy which happens when many features contain the same information.

Figure 18. Observing skewness

Using Python’s skew method, the skewness values for Flight Distance and Age can be examined. The skewness for Flight Distance is 1.1 and the skewness for Age is -0.0036. This is also illustrated at the bottom of Figure 18 where the skewness slips over the normal line. Age is normally distributed therefore the data fits tightly with the center line.

Figure 19. Log1p transformation

Using Python's `log1p` class skewness was reduced to -0.21 after Log transformation. Using the Yeo-Johnson transformation technique which is available in Python's `PowerTransformer` class, skewness was further reduced to -0.03 . However, since scaling will be performed later on, instead of log transforming the distance, the distance will be examined after scaling to see if it is then acceptable.

4.1.5 Correlation Matrix Heatmap

Heatmaps are effective for efficient visualization of patterns and relationships among high dimensional, multidimensional data (Gu et al., 2016). Correlation heatmaps can be used to identify possible relationships between variables and to gauge how strong these relationships are. These relationships can be both positive and negative relationships. Additionally, outliers can be found and linear and nonlinear correlations can be exploited. The Correlation Matrix measures the linear dependence between pairs of features. The correlation coefficients fall between -1 to 1 . Two variables have a perfect positive correlation if the coefficient value equals 1 , zero correlation if it equals 0 , and a perfect negative correlation if the value is -1 .

Figure 20. Correlation Heatmap

As for the Satisfaction target class the strongest positive or negative correlations exist between Online checkin (0.50), and Class_Economy (-0.50). Online Checkin is the strongest and this is reflected in the analysis of feature importance later in the study. As for correlations between features, strong positive or negative correlations exist between Inflight Wifi and Online Booking (0.71), Food & Drinks and Seat Comfort (0.58), Food & Drinks and Inflight Entertainment (0.62), Food & Drinks and Cleanliness (0.66), Seat Comfort and Cleanliness (0.68), Seat Comfort and Inflight Entertainment (0.61), Inflight Entertainment and Cleanliness (0.69), Onboard Service and Inflight Service (0.55), Baggage Handling and Inflight Service (0.63), Type_of_Travel_Personal_Travel and Class_Economy (0.55).

Examining the correlations Satisfaction levels are most influenced by online/mobile check-in options and passengers in Economy Class. Economy Class has a negative correlation with Satisfaction which means there are service issues with customers who fly in Economy Class. A strong relationship between inflight WiFi and online booking likely indicates that customers who book online likely purchase or reserve WiFi service as well. Unsurprisingly, the inflight services related to passenger comfort such as entertainment, seat comfort and cleanliness are positively correlated.

4.1.6 LASSO Regression & LASSO Path

Predictors	Coefficients
Age	-0.00013384
Flight Distance	2.29E-05
Inflight Wifi	0.046641111
Dep/Arr Times	-0.013355682
Online Booking	-0.020332358
Gate Location	0
Food and Drinks	0
Online Checkin	0.085675408
Seat Comfort	0.006336246
Inflight Entertainment	0.027918196
Onboard Service	0.033974922
Legroom	0.034009412
Baggage Handling	0.012092759
Airport Checkin	0.032695752
Inflight Service	0.007830932
Cleanliness	0.01587827
Departure Delay	0.00032371
Arrival Delay	-0.000832801
Total Delay	0
Route_Shorthaul	0
Customer Type_Repeat Customer	0.176942409
Type of Travel_Personal Travel	-0.289631332
Class_Economy	-0.11368485

Figure 21. Regression coefficients

The Correlation Heatmap was previously examined for any notable relationships between predictors and the target. The LASSO plot is also useful in confirming variables that are important in building the model by analyzing the coefficients of the features to identify which are most important. Initially, the raw coefficient values in Figure 21 are examined prior to running the LASSO regression and the LASSO Path plot to understand the actual values the LASSO will be using. One of the more frequently reported statistical methods involves correlation analysis where a correlation coefficient is reported representing the degree of linear association between two variables (Taylor, 1990). A regression coefficient describes the size and direction of the

relationship between a feature variable and the target variable. Coefficients are interpreted as the effect of each variable on the target variable, if all of the other independent variables are held constant. The logistic regression coefficient β related with n input X is the expected change in log odds of having the outcome per unit change in X (the input). So increasing the input by 1 unit multiplies the odds of having the outcome by e^β . The sign of each coefficient indicates the direction of the relationship between a predictor variable and the response variable. A feature with a negative coefficient has a negative correlation to the target class. In this study Type of Travel Personal Travel and Class Economy both have negative coefficients in the regression model. In binary classification it is not recommended to use the p-value to select the features. The null hypothesis of the logit model is that all the coefficients of the features are 0. Therefore, it is a simultaneous testing. Disposing of features can result in change of the distribution for the original model and features. Due to the correlation among the variables, you cannot conclude from p-values and say that the particular feature is important or not important.

The purpose of the LASSO (least absolute shrinkage and selection operator) regression analysis is to improve the predictability and interpretability of the statistical model by performing both variable selection and regularization. Regression models' predictability and interpretability were improved with the introduction of Lasso. For use in a model, it chooses a smaller set of the known covariates (TIBSHIRANI, 1997). The aim is to reduce the variable space and select the best predictors to be included in the final model. The L1 Norm on the LASSO Path graph can tell us which value of the L1 norm yields the model with best predictive ability. It's important to understand that LASSO Path does not tell us the best predictors. However, generally the variables that enter the model early are the most predictive and variables that enter the model later are less important. Visually, two conditions can help identify a poor predictor on the LASSO Path plot. If the predictor's line enters late e.g. after the 0.8 coefficient and also continues to hug the 0.0 coef axis, that same predictor will have a low coef output of `0.000` or `0.0`. Meanwhile, if a predictor enters late, but sharply decreases or increases away from the axis, it still has potential to be a good performing predictor.

Figure 22. LASSO Path plot

Using both the LASSO regression model's coef outputs and the LASSO Path graph, the seemingly poor predictors are Age, Gate Location, Flight Distance, Food and Drinks, Total Delay, Route_Shorthaul. This doesn't mean these predictors will not be used in the final model building. It's an additional step in identify the least helpful predictors.

In the end, the only predictors not included from the original dataset were Age, Gender, and Gate Location. Unfortunately, the two new features Total Delay and the Route with its Shorthaul and Longhaul cardinal units didn't make the cut. The final predictors used moving forward were 'Satisfaction', 'Age', 'Flight Distance', 'Inflight Wifi', 'Dep/Arr Times', 'Online Booking', 'Gate Location', 'Food and Drinks', 'Online Checkin', 'Seat Comfort', 'Inflight Entertainment', 'Onboard Service', 'Legroom', 'Baggage Handling', 'Airport Checkin', 'Inflight Service', 'Cleanliness', 'Departure Delay', 'Arrival Delay', 'Total Delay', 'Route_Shorthaul', 'Customer Type_Repeat Customer', 'Type of Travel_Personal Travel', 'Class_Economy'.

5.0 Model Building

The data has been processed and the predictors selected. The next stage is to build and select the models. This study examines 10 machine learning models. Logistic Regression, k-nearest neighbors algorithm (k-NN), Gaussian Naïve Bayes (GaussianNB), Decision Tree, Random Forest, Ensemble, AdaBoost, XGBoost, LightGBM, and an additional Neural Network, specifically the Keras Neural Network API. There are a couple of steps needed before building the models.

5.1 Training

Before model building, the dataset needs to be split into training and test sets. Training a model entails learning (deciding) appropriate values for each weight and bias from labeled samples. A common split is 80% for training and 20% for testing. Risk reduction is the technique by which a machine learning algorithm constructs a model in supervised learning by analyzing several examples and looking for a model that minimizes loss. The consequence of a poor prediction is loss. In other words, loss is a measure of how poorly the model predicted a single case outcome like Spam or Not Spam, Satisfied or Not Satisfied. The loss is zero if the model's prediction is accurate; otherwise, the loss is anything above zero. Finding a set of weights and biases that, on average, have low loss across all examples is the aim of training a model. Many machine learning techniques separate the original data into training and test sets, using the training set to train the model and the test set to validate the model. One popular validation technique is K-fold cross-validation. In K-fold cross-validation, the original data is randomly divided into K parts, K of which are used for model training in each round while K of which are kept for model validation. All of these components are utilized to validate the model, and the final estimate is determined by averaging the verification results (Wei et al., 2019). Python's sklearn package has a method designed for splitting the sample population called "train_test_split".

5.2 Data Standardization

Standardization becomes useful when predictors have large differences between their value ranges and when they are measured in different measurement units. These differences in initial feature ranges cause problems for many machine learning models. If one of the features has a wide range of values, the algorithm calculations will be influenced by this feature.

Standardization of a dataset is a common requirement for many machine learning estimators as the estimators might behave badly if the predictors do not more or less look like standard normally distributed data. This study uses sklearn's StandardScaler function which standardizes features by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance. The standard score of a sample x is calculated as $z = (x - u) / s$, where u is the mean of the training samples or zero if set, and s is the standard deviation of the training samples or one if one is set (scikit-learn developers, 2022). By calculating the pertinent statistics on the samples in the training set, centering and scaling are applied independently to each feature. The mean and standard deviation are recorded to be used later in the pipeline. When scaling the airlines dataset, the transform is trained on the training data first then the test data is transformed by that training.

5.3 Hyper-parameter Tuning

Hyperparameter tuning is the process of determining the best model design by adjusting the parameters that make up that model design. The hyper-parameters might examine challenges such as the maximum depth for a decision tree, the minimum number of samples needed for a leaf-node in the decision tree, the optimum number of trees in a tree classifier, how many neurons are optimum for the Keras neural network and other areas. Before setting out to build the models, those parameters need to be decided on to maximize accuracy of the predictions later on. Grid search is a method that is used for hyper-parameter tuning. Machine Learning is about comparing a selection of models and trying to find the best one. There are a few popular grid searching methods such as GridSearchCV, BayesSearchCV and RandomizedSearchCV. The building process in this research uses the BayesSearchCV method. In practice, compared with the other the search methods grid search performs poorly (Bergstra and Bengio, 2012). BayesSearchCV uses Bayesian optimization to search the hyper-parameters search space using the information from the previous iterations. Other methods, such as grid and random search, traverse across the search space either exhaustively or randomly (Brivio, 2020).

“In Bayesian optimization, the number of iterations are the number of function evaluations performed. Bayesian optimization with 25 executions is competitive in accuracy and better in training time than the more exhaustive grid search of 110 executions. Bayesian optimization is small averaging 1-2 seconds per execution.” (Porter, n.d.).

5.4 Grid Search Hyper-parameter results

Logit

Logit model parameters use for hyper-tuning:

‘C’: [0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10]

‘penalty’: [‘l1’, ‘l2’]

‘max_iter’: [100, 300, 500]

‘solver’: [‘newton-cg’, ‘lbfgs’, ‘liblinear’, ‘sag’, ‘saga’]

Returned config:

Config: {‘C’: 0.1, ‘penalty’: ‘l1’, ‘solver’: ‘liblinear’}

KNN

KNN parameters used for searching:

‘n_neighbors’: (1,10, 1)

‘leaf_size’: (20,40,1)

‘p’: (1,2)

‘weights’: (‘uniform’, ‘distance’)

‘metric’: (‘minkowski’, ‘chebyshev’)

Returned config:

Config: {‘leaf_size’: 20, ‘metric’: ‘minkowski’, ‘n_neighbors’: 10, ‘p’: 1, ‘weights’: ‘distance’}

Gaussian NB

Gaussian NB parameters used for searching:

‘estimator__var_smoothing’: [1e-2, 1e-3, 1e-4, 1e-5, 1e-6, 1e-7, 1e-8, 1e-9, 1e-10, 1e-11, 1e-12, 1e-13, 1e-14, 1e-15]}

Returned config:

Config: {'var_smoothing': 0.01}

Decision Tree

Decision Tree parameters used for searching:

"criterion" :["gini", "entropy"]

"splitter" :["best", "random"]

"min_samples_leaf": [*np.arange(100, 1500, 100)]

"max_depth": [*np.arange(5, 20, 5)]

"max_features": [*np.arange(2, 24, 2)]

Returned config:

Config: {criterion='entropy', max_depth=15, max_features=22, min_samples_leaf=100}

Random Forest

Random Forest parameters for searching:

"n_estimators": [*np.arange(100, 2000, 200)]

"max_depth": [*np.arange(5, 20, 5)]

"max_features": [*np.arange(2, 24, 2)]

Returned config:

Config: {max_depth=15, max_features=8, n_estimators=1300}

AdaBoost

AdaBoost parameters for searching:

n_estimators": [1200, 1300, 1500]

learning_rate": [0.01, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3]

Returned config:

Config: {n_estimators=1000, learning_rate=0.1}

AdaBoost Decision Tree Base-learner

AdaBoost Decision Tree base-learner parameters for searching:

criterion" : ["gini", "entropy"]

min_samples_leaf": [10, 20, 50, 100]

max_depth": [13, 15, 17]
max_features": [5, 10, 15]

Returned config:

Config: {criterion='gini', max_depth=10, max_features=9, min_samples_leaf=75, splitter='random'}

LightGBM

LightGBM parameters for searching:

"n_estimators": [4000, 5000, 6000, 7000, 8000]
"learning_rate": [0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5]
"num_leaves": [*np.arange(700, 1000, 100)]
"max_depth": [*np.arange(16, 21, 2)]
"min_data_in_leaf": [*np.arange(10, 25, 50)]
"min_split_gain": [*np.arange(2, 6, 1)]
"bagging_fraction": [*np.arange(0.7, 0.95)]
"bagging_freq": [1]
"feature_fraction": [*np.arange(0.7, 0.95)]

Returned config:

Best Estimator: objective='binary'
bagging_fraction', 0.7
bagging_freq', 1
feature_fraction', 0.7
learning_rate', 0.2
max_depth', 16
min_data_in_leaf', 10
min_split_gain', 2
n_estimators', 8000
num_leaves', 900

XGBoost

XGBoost parameters for searching:

"subsample": [0.9, 1.0]

```
“colsample_bytree”: [0.7, 0.8, 0.9]
“max_depth”: [*np.arange(5, 10, 2)]
“min_child_weight”: [*np.arange(0, 6)]
“learning_rate”: [0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 0.2]
“n_estimators”: [500, 1000, 2000, 3000, 4000]
```

Returned config:

```
Config: {n_estimators=3000,learning_rate=0.01,max_depth=9,colsample_bytree=0.7,
min_child_weight=5, subsample=0.91}
```

Keras NN (Sequential)

Parameters:

```
keras.layers.Dense(22, input_dim=22, activation=tf.nn.relu, name = “Dense_1”),
keras.layers.Dense(22, activation=tf.nn.relu, name = “Dense_2”),
keras.layers.Dense(11, activation=tf.nn.relu, name = “Dense_3”),
keras.layers.Dense(1, activation=tf.nn.sigmoid, name = “sigmoid”)

(optimizer=tf.keras.optimizers.Adam(learning_rate=0.01),
    loss=tf.keras.losses.binary_crossentropy,
    metrics=[keras.metrics.Precision(), keras.metrics.Recall(), keras.metrics.Accuracy(),
keras.metrics.AUC()])
```

5.5 K-fold Cross-Validation

Cross-validation is a model validation method for determining how well the outcomes of a statistical analysis will transfer to a different set of data. It is one of the most widely used data resampling methods to estimate the true prediction error of models and to tune model parameters (Berrar, 2019). Even while it cannot stop your model from overfitting, it nonetheless is an effective method of measuring a realistic performance estimate. The K-fold Cross Validation method was used in this study. The function has a single input, k, that designates how many groups should be created from a given data sample. As a result, the process is frequently referred to as k-fold cross-validation. When a particular number for k is selected, it may be substituted for k in the pointer to the model. Therefore k=10 is used to refer to cross-validation by a 10-fold factor. In this training sklearn's Kfold function is used.

Model	Scoring	Score	Model	Scoring	Score
Logistic Regression	AUC	0.926316703	Ensemble	AUC	0.98569167
Logistic Regression	Precision	0.869291066	Ensemble	Precision	0.957023897
Logistic Regression	Recall	0.836942562	Ensemble	Recall	0.911219328
Logistic Regression	Accuracy	0.874509166	Ensemble	Accuracy	0.943659527
KNN	AUC	0.924280656	AdaBoost	AUC	0.993036156
KNN	Precision	0.854453831	AdaBoost	Precision	0.967560218
KNN	Recall	0.801102331	AdaBoost	Recall	0.941478991
KNN	Accuracy	0.854307834	AdaBoost	Accuracy	0.958654129
Gaussian NB	AUC	0.914977891	XGBoost	AUC	0.994751241
Gaussian NB	Precision	0.830987179	XGBoost	Precision	0.970900425
Gaussian NB	Recall	0.814925612	XGBoost	Recall	0.941542467
Gaussian NB	Accuracy	0.847599743	XGBoost	Accuracy	0.962340239
Decision Trees	AUC	0.987714352	LightGBM	AUC	0.993666346
Decision Trees	Precision	0.948477566	LightGBM	Precision	0.969650232
Decision Trees	Recall	0.914151949	LightGBM	Recall	0.937635307
Decision Trees	Accuracy	0.941089836	LightGBM	Accuracy	0.960155529
Random Forest	AUC	0.993746628	KerasNN	AUC	0.953085094
Random Forest	Precision	0.971869673	KerasNN	Precision	0.958034449
Random Forest	Recall	0.938970145	KerasNN	Recall	0.953085094
Random Forest	Accuracy	0.961676154	KerasNN	Accuracy	0.955244978

Figure 23. Cross validation scores

5.6 Novel Algorithms & Logit Model

5.6.1 Logit Model

The Logit model is a classifier that models the probability of one event out of two possible outcomes happening by having the the logarithm of the odds for the outcome be a linear combination of one or more inputs (features/predictors). In regression analysis, logistic regression is estimating the coefficients (parameters) in the linear combination.

(The parsimonious approach)

A simple model, also known as a stupid model, is the most basic model to start with. The baseline model. It is a model that is easy to set up, inexpensive (in terms of required RAM/CPU), and has a fair probability of providing satisfactory results. If that baseline model is having difficulty, you can learn from the errors and apply them in the next models. If a simple proves to be accurate, then you've potentially saved yourself from having to build a more robust model. If it performs poorly then it can help you identify problems with data more easily since there was no complex set up. Models should ideally be developed gradually, starting with simple assumptions and only adding complications as they become necessary. The intention being to learn what we can from this simple model and then to refine it gradually. This is also called "prototyping". The idea that it's best to quickly develop a working model even if it's imperfect. This is the same idea in software development (Pidd, 1996).

5.6.2 LightGBM

LightGBM, known as Light Gradient Boosting Machine, is an open source distributed gradient boosting framework for machine learning developed by Microsoft. It is based on decision tree algorithms and used for ranking, classification and other machine learning tasks. Sparse optimization, parallel training, various loss functions, regularization, bagging, and early stopping are just a few of the advantages that LightGBM has over XGBoost (Wikipedia, 2022). The way trees are built in the two differs significantly. Unlike the majority of previous implementations, LightGBM grows a tree row by row rather than level by level. Trees are instead grown leaf-wise. It selects the leaf it thinks will result in the greatest reduction in loss. As opposed to XGBoost, LightGBM does not use the popular sorted-based decision tree learning algorithm, which seeks the best split point on sorted feature values. Instead, LightGBM uses a highly optimized decision

tree learning algorithm based on histograms, which has significant performance advantages (Ke et al., 2017).

5.6.3 ADABOOST

The Freund and Schapire AdaBoost algorithm, which has applications in many other industries, was the first real-world boosting algorithm and is now one of the most popular and extensively studied. The concept behind the machine learning strategy known as “boosting” is to combine a number of very weak and faulty prediction rules to produce a highly accurate prediction rule (Freund and Schapire, 1995). Its performance can be enhanced by combining it with a variety of other learning methods. The results of the other learning algorithms called “base-learners” are merged to create a weighted total that represents the boosted classifier’s final results. AdaBoost is adaptive in that it modifies the weak learners in favor of instances that prior classifiers incorrectly classified. It may be less prone to the overfitting issue than other learning algorithms in particular situations. AdaBoost is frequently used to combine base learners like decision stumps, but it has been demonstrated that it can also combine strong base learners like deep decision trees well, leading to an even more precise model. Strong base-learners have been implemented in this study. Information collected during each point of the classification about the relative learning difficulty of each training sample is fed into the tree-growing algorithm such that later trees tend to focus on cases that are more difficult to categorize (Freund and Schapire, 1995).

5.6.4 XGBOOST

XGBoost is short for eXtreme Gradient Boosting. XGBoost is an implementation of gradient boosted decision trees designed to be performant (Friedman, 2001). Gradient tree boosting is a machine learning method that excels in a variety of practical applications. On many common classification benchmarks, tree boosting has been shown to produce cutting-edge results (Chen and Guestrin, 2016). With new enhancements like regularization, the model’s implementation provides the features of the scikit-learn and R implementations. Supported gradient boosting methods include three primary types. The learning rate is included in the gradient boosting algorithm. Sub-sampling using stochastic gradient boosting at the row, column, and column per split levels. Gradient boosting using regularization at both the L1 and L2 levels. The algorithm’s implementation was designed to use memory and computing resources efficiently.

5.6.5 Keras Neural Network (Sequential)

Keras is a high-level neural network API that was originally written in Python and can run on top of TensorFlow or Theano. It was created with the goal of allowing for quick experimentation (Arnold, 2017). Keras runs on top of the TensorFlow machine learning platform. It was created with the goal of allowing for quick experimentation as it is critical to be able to move quickly from idea to result when conducting research. Keras reduces developer cognitive load, allowing you to focus on the important parts of the problem. It adopts the principle that simple workflows should be quick and easy, while arbitrarily advanced workflows should be possible via a clear path that builds upon what you've already learned. It is used by organizations and companies including NASA, YouTube, or Waymo (Keras, 2022). Keras enables developers to concentrate on the fundamental concepts of deep learning, such as creating layers for neural networks, while handling the details of tensors, their shapes, and their mathematical aspects. There are two types of Keras frameworks, sequential APIs and functional APIs. The sequential API is based on the concept of a layer sequence. This is the most common usage of Keras and the framework that is used in this study. The sequential model can be thought of as a layer-by-layer stack (Manaswi, 2018).

5.7 Performance Metrics

All machine learning models are assessed on performance. These metrics are known as performance metrics or evaluation metrics, and they help evaluate the quality of the model.

5.7.1 Confusion Matrix

A Confusion Matrix, also known as an Error Matrix or a Contingency Table, is a performance measurement for machine learning classification problems where the output is binary such as 0 & 1. It is a 4x4 table-grid with four different possibilities of predicted and true values. It describes the performance of a model on a set of test data where the true values are known. It is very useful for measuring Recall, Precision, Specificity, Accuracy, as well as AUC-ROC curves.

Confusion Matrix		
	Actually Positive (1)	Actually Negative (0)
Predicted Positive (1)	True Positives (TPs)	False Positives (FPs)
Predicted Negative (0)	False Negatives (FNs)	True Negatives (TNs)

Figure 24. Confusion Matrix

Figure 25 illustrates the combinations of the true values and predicted values. They can be interpreted as follows:

- True Positives (TP): These are instances where the classifier predicted yes or 1. For example: Satisfied or Spam.
- True Negatives (TN): The classifier predicted no or 0, and the outcome is Not Satisfied or Not Spam.
- False Positives (FP): The classifier predicted yes or 1, but the outcome is really Not Satisfied or Not Spam. (Type I error).
- False Negatives (FN): The classifier predicted no or 0, but the outcome is really Satisfied or Spam. (Type II error).

5.7.2 Accuracy, Precision, Recall, Error, ROC

The outcomes from the Confusion Matrix can be measured and used as scores to estimate the models' performance. These scores are known as accuracy, precision, recall, error and ROC. ROC is discussed below with Figure 31. XGBoost ROC Curve.

- Accuracy: Overall, how often is the classifier correct?
 $(TP+TN)/total$
- Misclassification Rate (Error Rate): Overall, how often is it wrong?
 $(FP+FN)/total$
- True Positive Rate (Sensitivity or Recall): How often does it predict yes correctly?
 $TP/actual\ yes$

- False Positive Rate: How often does it predict yes incorrectly?
FP/actual no
- True Negative Rate (Specificity): How often does it predict no correctly?
TN/actual no
- Precision: How often is it correct when the model predicts yes?
TP/predicted yes
- Prevalence: How often does the yes outcome occur in the sample?
Actual yes total

6.0 Model Performance

6.1 Logistic Regression

The Logit model is the simple model. The base performance that all following models are aiming to best.

Figure 25. Confusion Matrix of the Simple Logit Model

Looking at the Confusion Matrix in Figure 25, the Logit simple model predicted Not Satisfied correctly 13,337 times and incorrectly 1874 times. It predicted Satisfied correctly 9379 times and incorrectly 1386 times. This is the base model therefore the low scores are not surprising.

Scoring	Score
AUC	0.869767533
Accuracy	0.874095319
Recall	0.836591035
Precision	0.868944428

Figure 26. Logit Model (simple model) evaluation metrics on the train set

Scoring	Score
AUC	0.869664104
Accuracy	0.874499538
Recall	0.833466631
Precision	0.871249419

Figure 27. Logit Model (simple model) evaluation metrics on the test set

Scoring	Score
AUC	0.926317
Precision	0.869291
Recall	0.836943
Accuracy	0.874509

Figure 28. Logit Performance scores after cross validation

6.2 XGBoost

Figure 29. XGBoost Confusion Matrix

In Figure 29, XGBoost predicted Not Satisfied correctly 14,696 times and incorrectly only 736 times. It predicted Satisfied correctly 10,517 times and incorrectly only 27 times.

Figure 30. XGBoost Probability Threshold score

XGBoost Training on the validation set in Figure 30. Precision and Recall using a probability threshold set to 0.5 and 0.7.

Scoring	Threshold	Score
Precision	0.5	0.973081
Precision	0.7	0.990033
Recall	0.5	0.940329
Recall	0.7	0.916601

Figure 31. Soft Voting threshold scores for XGBoost

Figure 32. XGBoost ROC Curve

Another score used in this study is the ROC Curve or ROC AUC. This is a widely used graph that summarizes the performance of a classifier over all possible thresholds. It is graphed by plotting the True Positive Rate, the (y-axis), against the False Positive Rate, the (X-axis), the threshold is varied for assigning observations to a given class for example the commonly used 0.5 and 0.7 thresholds. XGBoost's Confusion Matrix in Figure 30 supports the observations made by the ROC Curve. It can boost the weaker learner using more performant parallel computing and optimized algorithms. Gradient boosting is superior in XGBoost. In the algorithm, one tree attempts to predict the outcome, another tree makes an attempt to predicts residuals on the first tree (the outcome of the loss function), a third tree makes an attempt to predict the residuals of the second tree, and that continues on. That's the gradient boosting part of XGBoost. Given that this iterative prediction process might result in overfitting, XGBoost penalizes complexity by adding regularization to the loss function. A better performance is displayed by classifiers that provide curves that are closer to the top-left corner. In In Figure 32, the XGBoost ROC is very good.

Feature importance describes methods that rate predictors or features according to how well they are able to predict a given target class. Correlation scores, coefficients generated as part of linear models are a few common examples of the many different types and sources of feature importance scores. In predictive modeling, feature importance scores offer insight into the data, insight into the model, and is the foundation for eliminating predictors (features) that do not contribute to the accuracy of the model. Removing these predictors can increase a predictive

model's efficiency and effectiveness in solving the problem as well as provide better hardware performance.

features	importance
Online Checkin	0.23351274
Inflight Wifi	0.12254347
Type of Travel_Business Travel	0.121810965
Type of Travel_Personal Travel	0.09963284
Class_Business	0.08954038
Class_Economy	0.061153807
Customer Type_New Customer	0.053383265
Customer Type_Repeat Customer	0.053195093
Inflight Entertainment	0.03825289
Online Booking	0.01926611
Seat Comfort	0.014995197
Airport Checkin	0.014434311
Cleanliness	0.012941578
Baggage Handling	0.012841876
Onboard Service	0.011154212
Inflight Service	0.010938729
Legroom	0.009685405
Dep/Arr Times	0.008888614
Food and Drinks	0.003901499
Arrival Delay	0.003180268
Flight Distance	0.00263151
Departure Delay	0.002115242

Figure 33. XGBoost feature importance statistics

In descending order, the various features are given with their importance score in Figure 33. It's important to understand that while some features are more important or maybe influence an outcome more than other features, it does not necessarily mean that eliminating the most important feature from the final prediction test will result in a significant change in outcome. It is the difference in the scores is the main factor. In this study for example, if all of the customer service ratings for all services were a perfect 5, but the most important feature "Online Checkin" was set in the test as having a rating of 1 in the final prediction tests, the prediction could still be "Satisfied". The difference in the range of the feature importance scores in this analysis are not huge so the outcomes of the test predictions may not be influenced by a single predictor so easily.

Figure 34. XGBoost Feature Importance plot

6.3 LightGBM

Scoring	Score
AUC	0.993666
Precision	0.96965
Recall	0.937635
Accuracy	0.960156

Figure 35. LightGBM Performance metrics

Figure 36. LightGBM Confusion Matrix

In Figure 36, LightGBM predicted Not Satisfied correctly 14,651 times and incorrectly only 896 times. It predicted Satisfied correctly 10,357 times and incorrectly only 72 times.

6.4 AdaBoost

Scoring	Score
AUC	0.993036
Precision	0.96756
Recall	0.941479
Accuracy	0.958654

Figure 37. AdaBoost Performance Metrics

Figure 38. AdaBoost Confusion Matrix

In Figure 38, AdaBoost predicted Not Satisfied correctly 14,723 times and incorrectly however, it incorrectly predicted Not Satisfied 4359 times which is very large. It predicted Satisfied correctly 6.894 times and incorrectly 0 times.

6.5 Keras NN (Sequential)

Keras/Tensorflow models are often run on high-performance systems having more computing power (RAM/CPU). In this research project, Keras was run on Google's Colaboratory TPU for performant training and modeling. The resulting recommended parameters from GridSearchCV fitting were then used in a regular notebook where the Keras model was trained and included with the other nine models in this study. Even with the help of Colab's TPU and RAM, while also using the recommend Tensorflow functions, GridSearchCV still required nearly 24 hours.

Colaboratory, or "Colab" for short, is a product from Google Research. Colab allows anybody to write and execute arbitrary python code through the browser, and is especially well suited to machine learning, data analysis and education ~ (Google 2022).

Figure 39. Keras NN Training and Validation Accuracy

In Figure 39, the metrics history of the neural network training with the validation data as it takes place can be plotted. Accuracy counts correct/incorrect, therefore if the neural network changes its opinion on a sample, the accuracy will jump suddenly. This is the reason for the sporadic jumps in the oscillation of the orange validation line. Validation loss is not increasing meaning it is not overfitting.

Scoring	Score
AUC	0.924281
Precision	0.854454
Recall	0.801102
Accuracy	0.854308

Figure 40. Keras NN Performance Metrics

Figure 41. Keras NN Confusion Matrix

In Figure 41, the NN predicted Not Satisfied correctly 14,590 times and incorrectly only 957 times. It predicted Satisfied correctly 10,296 times and incorrectly only 133 times.

Figure 42. Keras ROC Curve

The definition of ROC was discussed in the previous ROC plot of XGBoost in Figure 32. In Figure 42, the trade-off between specificity (1-FPR) and sensitivity (TPR) is depicted also by the ROC curve. A better performance is displayed by classifiers that provide curves that are closer to the top-left corner. In this Keras neural network it is very good. With a baseline classifier, it is

anticipated to provide points on or near the diagonal (FPR=TPR). This would indicate no predictive value. The test is less accurate the closer the curve gets to the ROC's 45-degree diagonal.

7.0 Model Results

Figure 43. Performance summary of 10 ML models

After training, standardization, grid-search, hyper-parameter tuning, cross-validation and running all 10 models, the winner is XGBoost. XGBoost has been proven to outperform other machine learning models especially in healthcare where classification necessitates the highest accuracy in all evaluations metrics (Ogunleye and Wang, 2019). XGboost algorithm is superior to other algorithms in accuracy and time and has great research value (Zhang et al., 2019). As discussed above in the Keras description, running Keras NN on a more performant system could yield better results.

Model	Scoring	Score
Logistic Regression	AUC	0.926316703
Logistic Regression	Precision	0.869291066
Logistic Regression	Recall	0.836942562
Logistic Regression	Accuracy	0.874509166
KNN	AUC	0.924280656
KNN	Precision	0.854453831
KNN	Recall	0.801102331
KNN	Accuracy	0.854307834
Gaussian NB	AUC	0.914977891
Gaussian NB	Precision	0.830987179
Gaussian NB	Recall	0.814925612
Gaussian NB	Accuracy	0.847599743
Decision Trees	AUC	0.987714352
Decision Trees	Precision	0.948477566
Decision Trees	Recall	0.914151949
Decision Trees	Accuracy	0.941089836
Random Forest	AUC	0.993746628
Random Forest	Precision	0.971869673
Random Forest	Recall	0.938970145
Random Forest	Accuracy	0.961676154

Model	Scoring	Score
Ensemble	AUC	0.98569167
Ensemble	Precision	0.957023897
Ensemble	Recall	0.911219328
Ensemble	Accuracy	0.943659527
AdaBoost	AUC	0.993036156
AdaBoost	Precision	0.967560218
AdaBoost	Recall	0.941478991
AdaBoost	Accuracy	0.958654129
XGBoost	AUC	0.994751241
XGBoost	Precision	0.970900425
XGBoost	Recall	0.941542467
XGBoost	Accuracy	0.962340239
LightGBM	AUC	0.993666346
LightGBM	Precision	0.969650232
LightGBM	Recall	0.937635307
LightGBM	Accuracy	0.960155529
KerasNN	AUC	0.953085094
KerasNN	Precision	0.958034449
KerasNN	Recall	0.953085094
KerasNN	Accuracy	0.955244978

Figure 44. Performance metrics for all classifiers

8.0 Discussion

Now that the data analysis findings are evident, theory and literature on the customer satisfaction study can be looked at considering the results of the binary classification analysis for a discussion.

Customer value is certainly the key to customer satisfaction, loyalty and market dominance. This study demonstrates the importance to the managing director of an airline of prioritizing customer service factors and elements into an airline business' overall strategy to improve airline quality (AIRQUAL). Providing exceptional customer service can give an airline a competitive edge. If managed carelessly, poor quality customer service can harm a business' operations and reputation (Mouawad and Kleiner, 1996). In this study cleanliness was found to not to be an important feature. Given the fact that these surveys were conducted years before the pandemic, and also the fact that the hotel & tourism industry is already onboard with including cleanliness as part of their marketing strategy (Jiang and Wen, 2020), it is evident that the airline industry will need to consider customer service more seriously in this new environment of cautiousness and concern for health safety.

Low-cost airlines are notorious either for poor customer service or the absence of services. Passengers are consistently frustrated with poor service including flight attendant service. Passenger satisfaction and dissatisfaction factors differ depending on cabin class flown, the purpose of travel and the ease and convenience to which a customer can book flights and extra

inflight services. Inflight services, reliable service provided by the cabin crew, value and low price are the most important factors for economy, premium and low-cost passengers (Sezgen et al., 2019). However, since available research has shown that ticket price has no impact on the loyalty and satisfaction of business class passengers (Jiang and Zhang, 2016), airlines will need to ensure that the extra luxuries and services provided in business class are always of top quality. Passengers in first or business class are more concerned about seat comfort, food and beverages, and in-flight entertainment. Passengers in economy class are more concerned about the value for money. (Punel et al., 2019). Business travelers and travelers on leisure also have different expectations and standards. Leisure travelers are generally having experiences in a tourist bubble with tourist guides, family, friends, et al., and mainly have social interactions with staff who are trained to communicate with tourists (Radojevic et al., 2018). With this outlook, the leisure traveler perceives customer value differently. The leisure traveler puts more importance on the value they are getting for their money spent. That value is an extension of products and services. Business travelers often lack this tourist bubble and have higher expectations on interactions with people responsible for providing higher levels of service therefore business travelers value tangibles that offer comfort more than value for money.

Check-in counters at the airport are generally overwhelmed with frustrated passengers. In addition, the number of check-in counters are usually not proportional to passenger load. These factors influence the performance of check-in counters and reservation service operators have to focus their attention on reducing waiting times in order to improve customer satisfaction (Putri et al., 2017). Additionally, the need for human interaction is not important in travelers' airport experience and satisfaction (Taufik and Hanafiah, 2019). Self check-in, defined as mobile check-in, web check-in and kiosk check-in, can increase customer satisfaction because it reduces airport wait times while traditional check-in services at the airport result in customer dissatisfaction (Wittmer, 2011). It is mainly offered to reduce costs, speed and enhance the customer experience. Self-service puts control into the hands of customers (Chen et al., 2015) and also improves the airline's image as it is considered to be innovative. This study also revealed that online check-in was the most important feature which supports the available research.

Wi-Fi cannot always be available especially on international long-haul flights, but it does play an important part in customers satisfaction. In fact, it plays a part in customer loyalty. Research has shown that there is a willingness to pay for Wi-Fi service (Reyes-Menendez et al., 2018). This is likely why online check-in is highly correlated with Inflight Wi-Fi. Customers are willing to pay for

and hope to be able to reserve Wi-Fi service on their journeys. It has also been shown that customers will be dissatisfied with the overall customer service experience if the performance of Wi-Fi is poor. Wi-Fi service has a strong impact on customer loyalty and retention. The quality of the Wi-Fi service also influences customer satisfaction where customers equate a higher quality in the Wi-Fi service to higher customer value and company image (Reyes-Menendez et al., 2018). The rankings of the feature importance of Wi-Fi in this research also supports this theory.

9.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings to the question, "Does measuring service quality factors help determine customer satisfaction?" is yes. The customers repeated choice to stay loyal to a business is why and how a company maintains its success. That repeated choice is a result of the service quality an airline delivers. Customers' perception of service quality is defined by air-travel service quality (AIRQUAL) dimensions such as tangibles, reliability, responsiveness assurance and empathy (Parasuraman et al., 1988). These dimensions are characterized by:

- The appearance of an aircraft's cabin, the appearance of personnel, equipment.
- The ability to deliver and perform inflight service dependably and as advertised.
- The willingness to provide the airline quality service that was promised.
- Cabin crew and airport personnel's knowledge and courtesy and their ability to demonstrate and instill trust and confidence, good communication, understanding and individual attention.

The aforementioned dimensions should be considered as part of the paradigm and ideals of an airline company and also be integrated into an airline's mission statement. Value proposition describes the benefits customers can expect from products and services (Osterwalder et al., 2015). The value proposition is the full package or of value that a business promises to deliver and is what is marketed to current and future customers. The value proposition differentiates an airline's brand and establishes itself in the industry (Li, 2007). The success of one value proposition is closely linked to the influence a business model has on the ability to deliver service.

Business Customer Predictions

Prediction Case 1: Repeat business customers flying in Business Class

If a repeat customer traveling on business and flying in Business Class, rated all services 3 (neutral/dissatisfied) out of 5 except for Wi-Fi, Food & Drinks and Online Check-in where they rated 5 out of 5, they would still be satisfied with their flight.

Prediction Case 2: New business customers flying in Business Class

If that same passenger in case 1 were a new customer, they would not have been satisfied with the flight. As discussed in the introduction, this survey counts a 3 rating as neutral or dissatisfied but for the sake of this study, it is labeled as Not Satisfied because being neutral is in fact not being satisfied.

Prediction Case 3: Repeat business customers flying in Business Class

This next prediction is surprising. If a repeat customer traveling on business and flying in Business Class, rated all services 1 out of 5 except for Legroom where they rated Legroom (5), they would still be satisfied with their flight. Since a passenger in Business Class would most likely rate Legroom a 5, maybe these customers are already satisfied with being in Business Class. The research also found that business passengers don't have the same value for money thought process as economy passengers.

Leisure Customer Predictions

Prediction Case 1: New leisure customers flying in Economy Class

If a new customer traveling on leisure and flying in Economy Class, rated Flight Delay, Online Checkin, Wi-Fi, Seat Comfort and Cleanliness excellent (5) and the rest (3), they would be a satisfied customer.

Prediction Case 2: New leisure customers flying in Economy Class

If the same customer in case 1 of leisure customers rated the Delay (3), they would not be satisfied.

Prediction Case 3: Repeat leisure customers flying in Economy Class

If the same customer in case 2 of leisure customers was a repeat customer, they would also not be satisfied.

Prediction Case 4: Repeat leisure customers flying in Economy Class

If a repeat customer traveling on leisure and flying in Economy Class rated all services excellent (5) but Flight Delay (3) or less, they would not be satisfied.

What these predictions say is that even though Type of Travel, Online Check-in and Wi-Fi are the most important features, they do not stand alone. Just as they were in the model and in real life, they are synergistic in the formation of a customer satisfaction outcome. Although Flight Delays were far down the list of important features, flight delays still changed the predictions when adjusted in concert with all the other features.

Further recommendations include re-designing a value proposition with marketing emphasizing the airline's understanding of customers' expectations of cleanliness and health safety. Essentially, describing how the airline intends to create value for the customer. "Fear of illness, economic damage, and stigma have had a devastating impact on the travel industry and have caused a significant reduction in both business and leisure travel." (Lamb et al., 2021). In a post-pandemic setting, consideration of social and emotional perspectives of airline passengers such as trust, fear will be more important. Cleanliness and etiquette will be high on the list of customer expectations. Re-designing a value proposition will allow an airline to understand the patterns of value creation. This means organizing information about what customers want and expect. Managing Directors need to ensure everyone from marketing, sales and operations is aligned and sharing the same vision. Improving service quality is dependent on the airline's ability to meet up to customers' expectations.

Loyalty is a repeated choice (Dolnicar et al., 2011). However as was discussed in the research regarding an airline's business model, an airline's ability to deliver an expected service is ancillary to the internal and external relationships an airline has with inter-agencies and business partners which provides further challenges. To be able to continue providing the quality service for which customers in turn will show their loyalty for, airlines will have to work closer with their partners and agencies to make sure they can deliver on their promises.

I also recommend that an airline's research team implementing the study run the neural network on a dedicated TPU or GPU instance to better take advantage of the Keras neural network API. The Colab TPU that was used was on the Colab Pro+ plan is less performant compared with Google Cloud AI instances or other cloud services. It is very possible that given more processing power, the Keras NN model would outperform XGBoost.

The study and research conclude that managing directors of airlines need to understand that all aspects of customer service aboard airplanes and in the airport are important to maintaining a high level of customer satisfaction and that any combination of failure points can create customer churn and in turn damage the image of their airline. This is especially true of customers traveling on leisure in Economy Class. Those customers are very value conscious customers unlike business customers where they are mainly concerned with paying for their Business Class ticket and getting to where they want to go. Being in Business Class, they are already mostly satisfied. Managers and marketing directors have to make greater efforts in making leisure customers in Economy Class feel like they are getting a lot of value. This holds especially true in a post-pandemic market where customers are more discriminating and discerning than ever before.

The results from this study offer informative insights to the subject of customer satisfaction dimensions in the airline sector. This is knowledge that if regarded as substantial and relevant, can create more positive travel experiences for everyone.

Albert Einstein once said, "Try not to become a man of success. Rather become a man of value". In the context of airline service quality, one could say, "Try not to become an airline of success. Rather become an airline of value".

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